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Effect of Formulation on the Release Kinetics of the Antibiotics from Biocompatible Ceramics

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Release kinetics of a drug from the ceramic drug delivery carrier depends on various parameters such as nature of the ceramic, binder, porosity of the ceramics, particle size of the ceramic and, solubility as well as nature of the drug. In the present study effect of formulation on the release kinetics of the drug from hydroxyapatite, the carrier was studied. Hydroxyapatite and Zirconia were taken as ceramic carriers and the model drugs taken for comparison are ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and levofloxacin whereas polyvinyl alcohol was added as a binder. Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride shows a sustained release whereas levofloxacin shows burst release from the ceramic drug carrier. The percentage of polyvinyl alcohol added to the drug played a vital role as a higher concentration of the polymer affects the stability of the drug carrier. Hydroxyapatite/zirconia composite shows sustained release (29%) when compared to pure hydroxyapatite (43%) and zirconia (37%) after 6 hours of immersion in simulated body fluid. Release kinetics shows that the solubility of the drug, concentration of the binder, and the ratio of ceramics in the composites decides the release kinetics of the drug from the drug delivery carrier.

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Introduction

Bone infections occur frequently during bone tissue regeneration due to bacterial attacks [1]. Osteomyelitis, septic arthritis, and prosthetic joint infections are among the most prevalent infections, with *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (*S. epidermidis*) being the most common agents [2]. While ceramic has traditionally been utilised to restore bone abnormalities as an implant material [3] or as a coating on metallic implants [4], absorbed chemicals such as growth factors [5] or antibiotics [6] can improve their efficacy. As a result, drug delivery (DD) can be used to promote bone regeneration [7, 8], and ceramic can be utilized as a drug delivery system (DDS or drug carrier) [9].

The drug release rate is an important concept in DD. Diffusion,

dissolution, swelling [10], affinity [11], and ion exchange [12] can all be used to regulate the rate at which a drug is released. In addition, temperature, pH, ionic strength, ultrasound, electricity, and magnetic field may all pinpoint drug release rate in a stimuli-responsive system [13]. Material properties, such as pore size and surface changes, can also impact drug release rates [14].

Bioactive ceramics can be useful in bone repair, owing to their capacity to deposit apatite and hence have a comparable composition to bone. Hydroxyapatite (HAp), an inorganic component of bone [15], is one of the most investigated bioactive ceramics. HAp is commonly used as a DDS for preventing bone infections [16]. Nanoparticles and nanostructured materials are currently attracting attention among researchers [17]. As a result of the combination of bioactive ceramic and antibiotics, bone tissue regeneration is induced, as well as assist in bacterial infection prevention [18] and antibacterial action [19]. HAp has been used as DDS in a form of particles [20], microspheres [21,22], and sponges [23]. According to Changlu Xu et al. (2017), HAp sponge can be prepared by

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combining HAp powder with starch suspension via heating, adding a surfactant, and stirring, then drying and sintering. As a result, a sea sponge-like HAp scaffold was developed that functions as a medication carrier for bone healing. Polymer/HAp composites are used extensively in addition to pure HAp and ion-doped HAp [24, 25]. Yong-Guang Bi et al., for example, used the modified emulsion cross-link technique to create HAp/sodium alginate/chitosan composite microspheres [26]. According to cellular experiments using osteoblasts, the suggested material exhibited pH-sensitive sustained drug release and is a potential material for bone tissue creation.

Release patterns might impact treatment efficacy so that the medication concentrations should be kept within the therapeutic window [27]. In the case of bone-related applications, it is recommended that release should be continued [28] to give local release at the implant site. The initial burst release of ceramic drug carriers is followed by a continuous release [29], although this process may be regulated by polymer addition [30]. A. P. S. Prasanna and G. Devanand Venkatasubbu utilized a HAp/PVA/sodium alginate composite loaded with amoxicillin as a DDS against bacteria that cause bone infections [31]. The combination showed sustained release and excellent antibacterial action within 30 days. Also, we propose the incorporation of zirconia which is used in orthopedics [32]. This combination of bioactive and bioinert ceramic [33] results in composites with increased fracture toughness and improved biocompatibility.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of various formulations on the drug delivery behaviour of biocompatible ceramics. A cost-effective sol-gel combustion technique was used to prepare microcrystalline hydroxyapatite. The hydroxyapatite was used as a drug carrier in both its pure form and as a composite with biocompatible ceramics having various quantities of PVA as a binder. A thorough investigation was conducted to improve these characteristics to produce a long-term medication delivery carrier, capable of preventing bone infections.

Materials and Methods

Calcium nitrate, Tartaric acid, Ammonium hydroxide, Concentrated nitric acid, Diammonium hydrogen phosphate, Commercial zirconia, Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, Levofloxacin, double distilled water. All the chemicals were used as purchased without further purification and processing.

Synthesis of hydroxyapatite as a drug delivery carrier

The synthesis of hydroxyapatite was carried out by the sol-gel combustion method. Stock solutions of calcium nitrate (1M), tartaric acid (1M), ammonium hydrogen phosphate (1M), and ammonium hydroxide (1:1) were prepared in standard volumetric flasks. Initially, 20 mL of calcium nitrate and 40 mL of tartaric acid were mixed in a beaker using a magnetic stirrer. The pH of the resultant mixture was adjusted to 9.5 by dropwise addition of 1:1 NH_4OH . It was found that due to the change in the pH, the color of the solution turned milky. Later stoichiometric ratio of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ solution was added to the above mixture. Finally, the precipitated mixture of phosphates was dissolved by slow addition of con. HNO_3 until the pH becomes 1. This step was performed very carefully due to the evolution of fumes when nitric acid was added. Also, the milky color disappeared and a clear solution was obtained. The resultant solution was heated to 70°C and stirred until the formation of the transparent gel was noticed. The gel was aged and decomposed at 250°C in a preheated muffle furnace. The resultant precursor was calcined at 900°C for 2 h resulting in the formation of pure hydroxyapatite.

Sample preparation for drug delivery studies

The pure hydroxyapatite powder was passed through a mechanical shaker 63 μm sieve. The powders obtained after sieving were used to prepare samples for drug delivery studies. Hydroxyapatite (100 mg) was mixed with a 1 mg/mL solution of levofloxacin. The mixture was ground in an agate mortar and pestle to form a slurry. The slurry was dried at 2 h at 60°C and again ground to form a fine powder. The drug-loaded composite sample was pelletized by using a manual hydraulic press and compressed at 10 MPa for 5 minutes. A similar procedure was followed for preparing hydroxyapatite pellet loaded with ciprofloxacin hydrochloride. Same sample and preparation conditions were followed for both the drugs to avoid the difference in release kinetics due to other factors.

The influence of polymer addition on the drug release profile of hydroxyapatite was also studied. Hydroxyapatite and PVA were mixed in a 10:1 ratio (10% PVA) and 1 mg/mL solution of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride was added. This mixture was ground and led to the formation of a slurry. The slurry was dried at 60°C for 2 h and reground to obtain a fine powder. The drug-loaded composite was pelletized by compressing it at a pressure of 5 MPa for 5 minutes using a hydraulic press. Similarly, 50% PVA and hydroxyapatite samples (1:1 ratio) were prepared by following the same procedure. It can be noted that similar preparation conditions were followed for the samples containing different amounts of PVA to avoid the difference in release kinetics due to other factors.

Moreover, the release profile of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride from two different biocompatible ceramics was also evaluated along with the addition of 10% PVA. Hydroxyapatite chemically synthesized in the laboratory by combustion route and commercially purchased zirconia were taken in a 1:1 ratio and 0.1 mL of 10 % PVA as well as 1 mg/mL solution of Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride was also added. The mixture was ground to form a slurry. The slurry was dried at 60°C for 2 h in a hot air oven and the resultant dried product was again crushed down to a fine powder using mortar and pestle. The drug-loaded composite was pelletized by applying a pressure of 6 MPa for 5 minutes in a manually operated hydraulic press. The same procedure was followed for preparing pure hydroxyapatite and pure zirconia samples. The parameters selected for preparing drug delivery samples are expressed in table 1.

In vitro drug release studies

The drug release kinetics of samples was studied in a physiological environment having a similar plasma concentration to that of humans. Hence, the as-prepared samples were immersed in 50 mL simulated body fluid (pH 7.25) in an Erlenmeyer flask with a glass stopper. The SBF was prepared as per Kokubo et al.'s (2006) protocol [34]. The flasks were placed in an incubator maintained at 37.5 °C \pm 2°C and shaken at 60 strokes/min. The drug release behavior of the samples was assessed by withdrawing 10% of the simulated body fluid (SBF) from each sample at suitable intervals and replaced immediately with fresh SBF. Drug concentrations in the collected SBF from the samples were measured

Table 1: Sample details for studying drug release kinetics

Drug Carrier	Drug	PVA Content (%)
1 Pure HAp	Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride	-
	Levofloxacin Hydrochloride	-
2 Pure HAp	Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride	10
	Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride	50
3 Pure HAp	Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride	-
4 Pure ZrO ₂	Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride	10
5 HAp-ZrO ₂ Composite	Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride	-

spectrophotometrically by UV-Visible Spectrophotometer. The levofloxacin was measured at a wavelength of 288 nm whereas in the case of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride at 278 nm.

Characterization

The phase purity of the synthesized hydroxyapatite sample was analyzed in Siemens D-500 X-Ray Diffractometer, using Cu K α , Ni filtered radiation. The chemical nature and molecular bond structure of the synthesized samples were determined using FT-IR (Thermo Nicolet, Avatar 330 FTIR Spectrometer, USA) studies. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) technique was used to analyze the specific average surface area of the hydroxyapatite powders calcined at 900°C using a fully automated BET surface area analyzer (Micromeritics ASAP2020). The surface morphology was imaged using a Scanning electron microscope (Jeol JSM - 5600 LV). The drug release kinetics was measured using Hitachi, U-2800 Spectrophotometer, Japan.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of Hydroxyapatite

The phase purity of drug carrier hydroxyapatite was analyzed by powder XRD. The absence of secondary phases in the XRD pattern (figure 1) confirmed the formation of hydroxyapatite as a single-phase and was matched with the standard JCPDS data card (09-432). The structure was found to be hexagonal and lattice parameters were $a = 9.41 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 6.86 \text{ \AA}$. This was noticed to be similar to an earlier report [35-37].

The presence of functional groups associated with hydroxyapatite was analyzed by FT-IR spectroscopy as shown in figure 2. The FT-IR spectra revealed the substitution of carbonate ions in the phosphate site as weak bands of CO $_3^{2-}$ were observed at 870 cm $^{-1}$ and 1465 cm $^{-1}$. The stretching vibrations of the OH group were noticed around 3671 cm $^{-1}$ whereas its bending vibrations were found at 631 cm $^{-1}$. The characteristic stretching vibrations of the phosphate were observed ranging from 962 cm $^{-1}$ to 1089 cm $^{-1}$. The presence of bands ranging from 470 cm $^{-1}$ to 601 cm $^{-1}$ corresponds to bending vibrations of phosphate [36, 37].

Figure 3 represents the SEM micrograph recorded at the magnification of 10000X of the hydroxyapatite powder sample

Figure 1: XRD pattern of the hydroxyapatite

Figure 2: FT-IR spectra of the hydroxyapatite

sintered at 900°C. The surface of hydroxyapatite revealed particle agglomeration (submicron range) due to the sintering of hydroxyapatite at high temperatures. Hence, the agglomeration of particles not only resulted in heterogeneous particle size but also reduced the surface porosity. This characteristic property might assist in preventing the faster diffusion of loaded drugs and will favor sustainable drug release kinetics from the hydroxyapatite. The porosity measurement of calcined hydroxyapatite was carried out by the BET technique and the results were found to be similar to an earlier report [35].

The presence of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and levofloxacin in hydroxyapatite was analyzed by FT-IR spectroscopy (figure 4). The characteristic functional groups associated with ciprofloxacin hydrochloride, levofloxacin as well as hydroxyapatite was observed in all the samples. Also, the incorporation of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and levofloxacin in the hydroxyapatite matrix resulted in peak broadening at 1454 and 1466 cm $^{-1}$. Figure 4 (a) shows the stretching vibrations of C-F and characteristic vibration band of

Figure 3: SEM micrograph of the hydroxyapatite

Figure 4: FT-IR spectra of the drug-loaded hydroxyapatite

phenyl framework conjugation to -COOH of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride was found at 1260 and 1610 cm^{-1} . The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_c$ for carboxylic acid and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_p$ for pyridine associated with ciprofloxacin hydrochloride are 1707 and 1625 cm^{-1} [35]. In the case of hydroxyapatite containing levofloxacin (Fig. 4b) the characteristic peaks of C=O, aromatic C-H group were found at 1623 cm^{-1} and 2935 cm^{-1} respectively. The vibration band of C-N owing to stretching of amine was detected at 1294 cm^{-1} [38].

Drug release from pure hydroxyapatite

Release kinetics of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and levofloxacin were compared for the first six hours (figure 5) in simulated body fluid. Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride showed a smooth pattern of release whereas levofloxacin shows a burst release and 70% of the drug got released within the first hour of immersion itself. As the incubation time was extended the release kinetics of levofloxacin was slowed down. The overall percentage release of ciprofloxacin after 6 hours of immersion was nearly 50 % whereas levofloxacin showed 85%. The main reason for the difference in the release pattern of levofloxacin and ciprofloxacin was their solubility. Blokhina et al. reported the solubility of levofloxacin was found to be higher than ciprofloxacin in the physiological medium [39]. The potential reason for such behavior was the variation in the structure

of the central fragment of the molecule (a bicyclic fragment for ciprofloxacin whereas tricyclic for levofloxacin). Moreover, the reduced solubility of ciprofloxacin is related to its higher crystal lattice energy as compared to levofloxacin. Amongst both drugs, ciprofloxacin exhibited a sustained release pattern. This observation shows release kinetics is dependent on the solubility of the drugs and does not follow the same pattern for the same class of drugs.

Drug release from hydroxyapatite containing PVA

The composite containing 10% PVA was dried, powdered and it resulted in the formation of a free-flowing product and after compression, shiny as well as compact samples were obtained. The composite comprising 50% PVA forms flakes on drying and the pellet formed consists of blisters on the surface. When these samples were placed in the simulated body fluid, the composite with 10% PVA was stable whereas the composite with 50% PVA swelled and collapsed by releasing a lot of air bubbles [40, 41]. The release profile (figure 6) was found to be smooth for the sample containing 10% PVA whereas the specimen with 50% PVA showed complete release of drug within the first hour itself. This behavior indicates that an optimum amount of binder could be favorable to produce a stable sample and extending this limit could lead to swelling and collapse of the sample in the physiological environment.

Figure 5: Initial release kinetics of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and levofloxacin from the hydroxyapatite

Figure 6: Variation of release kinetics of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride from the drug carrier with respect to hydroxyapatite/polymer ratio

Figure 7: Variation of release kinetics of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride from the drug carrier with respect to the constituents

Drug release from biocompatible ceramics and their composites

Figure 7 represents pure hydroxyapatite had a uniform and fast release pattern as compared to the irregular and slow release from pure zirconia. Whereas the HAp-ZrO₂ composite showed a combination of slow and uniform release kinetics. In other words, the release of ciprofloxacin from HAp after 6 hours of immersion was ~ 43%, nearly 37% was noticed in the case of zirconia and HAp-ZrO₂ composite revealed about 29%. This behavior can be due to the combined effect of hydroxyapatite and zirconia which assisted in reducing the release of ciprofloxacin in the physiological environment. It can also be noted that the porosity of the sample is directly proportional to the drug delivery kinetics. Thus, the less

porous material synthesized in the current study assisted in releasing the drug in a sustained mode.

Literature survey indicated that hydroxyapatite is widely explored as a drug carrier but zirconia has attracted the attention of researchers on a very low scale. Moreover, HAp/zirconia composites are least studied and their drug release potential material is still unknown. The current study represents the possibility of using HAp/zirconia/PVA hybrid composite as a drug delivery carrier. Table 2 presents a detailed comparison of the drug release profile between the developed biomaterials and proposed in the present work.

An earlier study revealed that pure HAp demonstrated burst release of drug in 3 h [20], which was found to be similar to levofloxacin-loaded HAp microparticles. Further, HAp/polymer composites have shown an initial burst followed by sustained release [26, 31]. The HAp/10%PVA composite loaded with ciprofloxacin hydrochloride exhibited a similar release profile and cumulative releases within 6 h are compatible. Recently, a doxorubicin-encapsulated HAp/PVA nanocomposite was developed for repairing osteosarcoma-affected bone tissue [42]. The drug release from the nanocomposite was found to be ~12% even after 24 hours in phosphate buffer solution whereas the maximum drug release percentage was noticed to be nearly 29% after 4 days. But the release profile of the nanocomposites during the initial hours of immersion was not reported. Moreover, the biocompatibility [43,44] and mechanical stability [45] of PVA containing HAp composites have been explored but their drug release behavior is least studied. Thus, we attempted to perform a detailed investigation on the drug release kinetics of PVA containing HAp composites in SBF to fill the gap that exists in the literature.

In the case of zirconia, the irregular release profile is typical [46] alongside our observations. In comparison with published data, the HAp/zirconia/PVA composite developed in this work demonstrated a sustained drug release of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride. This study indicates that a minor alteration in the formulation can affect the entire drug release pattern of the drug

Table 2: Comparison of drug delivery profile of hydroxyapatite and zirconia with existing reports

	Drug Carrier	Additional details of the Drug Carrier	Polymer	Drug	Drug release behavior	Approximate cumulative release in 6 h	Reference
1	HAp	Microcrystalline	-	Levofloxacin	Burst till 70%	~85%	Present stu
			10% PVA	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride	Smooth pattern	~50%	
2	HAp	Inverse opal HAp	-	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride	Smooth, uniform, and fast release	~43%	[20]
			-	Amoxicillin	Burst 60% release in first 3 h	~80%	
3	HAp	Nanoparticles	Polyvinyl alcohol and sodium alginate	Amoxicillin	Lower release rate, but the profile is similar	~60%	[31]
4	HAp	Nanorods	Sodium alginate and chitosan	Doxorubicin hydrochloride	Initial burst due to high-rate release till 35%, later sustained release	~15%	[26]
5	Zirconia	Commercial	10% PVA	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride	pH-sensitive release, faster drug release in acid medium, fast within first 10 h, then sustained	~25%	[26]
6	Zirconia	Sol-gel synthesis	Polyethylene glycol	Indomethacin	Irregular and slow-release	~37%	Present stu
7	HAp and zirconia	HAp microparticles and commercial zirconia	10% PVA	Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride	Irregular initially burst release	~10%	[46]
					Regular, slow, sustained release	~29%	Present stu

carrier. This article provides valuable information about the key factors affecting the drug release kinetics of biocompatible ceramics. Thus, the combination of a facile preparatory route and good drug release behavior represents an analogous and advantageous biomaterial for treating bone infections.

Conclusion

The present study reports that the release kinetics of the drug is highly influenced by the formulation of a drug delivery system. The results showed that the release kinetics is dependent on the solubility of drugs and does not follow the same release pattern for the same class of drugs. Levofloxacin is reported to have a good pharmacokinetic profile when compared to ciprofloxacin. But in the current report levofloxacin showed a non-uniform release behavior whereas ciprofloxacin indicated a smooth release pattern. The burst release of levofloxacin in the medium was due to its higher solubility when compared to ciprofloxacin. Addition of polymer in excess amount affected the stability of the sample which became unsuitable for drug delivery applications. The addition of polymer at an optimum level not only enhanced the stability of the drug carrier but also resulted in an efficient drug delivery system. Moreover, the results revealed that the fabrication of a composite can facilitate the sustained release of antibiotics. The homogenous mixing of the therapeutic constituents with biocompatible ceramics and uniform loading of the drug indicated the current methodology as a cost-efficient procedure for the sustained release of antibiotics.

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References

- E. Seebach, K.F. Kubatzky, Chronic Implant-Related Bone Infections-Can Immune Modulation be a Therapeutic Strategy? *Front. Immunol.*, 10, 1724 (2019).
- M. Ribeiro, F.J. Monteiro, M.P. Ferraz, Infection of orthopedic implants with emphasis on bacterial adhesion process and techniques used in studying bacterial-material interactions, *Biomater.*, 2, 176-194 (2012).
- S. Mondal, U. Pal, 3D hydroxyapatite scaffold for bone regeneration and local drug delivery applications, *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.*, 53, 101131 (2019).
- X. Lin, J. Chen, Y. Liao, J.L. Pathak, H. Li, Y. Liu, Biomimetic Calcium Phosphate Coating as a Drug Delivery Vehicle for Bone Tissue Engineering: A Mini-Review, *Coatings.*, 10, 118 (2020).
- M. Dang, L. Saunders, X. Niu, Y. Fan, P.X. Ma, Biomimetic delivery of signals for bone tissue engineering, *Bone Res.*, 6, 1-12 (2018).
- M. Parent, H. Baradari, E. Champion, C. Damia, M. Viana-Trecant, Design of calcium phosphate ceramics for drug delivery applications in bone diseases: A review of the parameters affecting the loading and release of the therapeutic substance, *J. Control. Release.*, 252, 1-17 (2017).
- S.G. Rotman, D.W. Grijpma, R.G. Richards, T.F. Moriarty, D. Eglin, O. Guillaume, Drug delivery systems functionalized with bone mineral seeking agents for bone targeted therapeutics, *J. Control. Release.*, 268, 88-99 (2018).
- J. Chen, A. Ashames, M.A. Buabeid, K.M. Faehelebom, M. Ijaz, G. Murtaza, Nanocomposites drug delivery systems for the healing of bone fractures, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 585, 119477 (2020).
- A.Y. Cai, Y.J. Zhu, C. Qi, Biodegradable inorganic nanostructured biomaterials for drug delivery, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces.*, 7, 2000819 (2020).
- J. Siepmann, H. Kranz, R. Bodmeier, N.A. Peppas, HPMC-matrices for controlled drug delivery: A new model combining diffusion, swelling, and dissolution mechanisms and predicting the release kinetics, *Pharm. Res.*, 16, 1748-1756 (1999).
- K. Vulic, M.S. Shoichet, Affinity-based drug delivery systems for tissue repair and regeneration, *Biomacromolecules*, 15, 3867-3880 (2014).
- J. Claus, T. Eickner, N. Grabow, U. Kragl, S. Oschatz, Ion Exchange controlled drug release from polymerized ionic liquids, *Macromol. Biosci.*, 20, 2000152 (2020).
- G.H. Son, B.J. Lee, C.W. Cho, Mechanisms of drug release from advanced drug formulations such as polymeric-based drug-delivery systems and lipid nanoparticles, *J. Pharm. Investig.*, 47, 287-296 (2017).
- N. Subhpradha, M. Abudhahir, A. Aathira, N. Srinivasan, A. Moorthi, Polymer coated mesoporous ceramic for drug delivery in bone tissue engineering, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 110, 65-73 (2018).
- Y.H. Ho, K. Man, S.S. Joshi, M. V. Pantawane, T.C. Wu, Y. Yang, N.B. Dahotre, In-vitro biomineralization and biocompatibility of friction stir additively manufactured AZ31B magnesium alloy-hydroxyapatite composites, *Bioact. Mater.*, 5, 891-901 (2020).
- B. Ghiasi, Y. Sefidbakht, M. Rezaei, Hydroxyapatite for biomedicine and drug delivery, in: Rahmandoust M., Ayatollahi M. (eds) *Nanomaterials for Advanced Biological Applications. Advanced Structured Materials*, vol 104. Springer, Cham. (2019).
- N. Aminu, I. Bello, N.M. Umar, N. Tanko, A. Aminu, M.M. Audu, The influence of nanoparticulate drug delivery systems in drug therapy, *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.*, 60, 101961 (2020).
- C. Gao, S. Peng, P. Feng, C. Shuai, Bone biomaterials and interactions with stem cells, *Bone Res.*, 5, 17059 (2017).
- C. Soriano-Souza, H. Valiense, E. Mavropoulos, V. Martinez-Zelaya, A.M. Costa, A.T. Alves, M. Longuinho, R. Resende, C. Mourão, J. Granjeiro, M.H. Rocha-Leao, A. Rossi, M. Calasans-Maia, Doxycycline containing hydroxyapatite ceramic microspheres as a bone-targeting drug delivery system, *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. Part B Appl. Biomater.*, 108, 1351-1362 (2020).
- L. li Wang, Y. min Zhou, X. feng Wang, L. na Feng, X. Xin Liu, Preparation of inverse opal hydroxyapatite and drug delivery properties, *Chemistry Select.*, 5, 3815-3819 (2020).
- R. Chen, J. Shi, B. Zhu, L. Zhang, S. Cao, Mesoporous hollow hydroxyapatite capped with smart polymer for multi-stimuli remotely controlled drug delivery, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.*, 306, 110447 (2020).
- H. Huang, M. Du, J. Chen, S. Zhong, J. Wang, Preparation and characterization of abalone shells derived biological mesoporous hydroxyapatite microspheres for drug delivery, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C.*, 113, 110969 (2020).
- C. Xu, Z. Wei, H. Gao, Y. Bai, H. Liu, H. Yang, Y. Lai, L. Yang, Bioinspired Mechano-Sensitive Macroporous Ceramic Sponge for Logical Drug and Cell Delivery, *Adv. Sci.*, 4, 1600410 (2017).
- S. Vieira, S. Vial, R.L. Reis, J.M. Oliveira, Nanoparticles for bone tissue engineering, *Biotechnol. Prog.*, 11, 1253-1263 (2017).
- S. Mondal, S. V. Dorozhkin, U. Pal, Recent progress on fabrication and drug delivery applications of nanostructured hydroxyapatite, *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev. Nanomedicine Nanobiotechnology*, 10, 1504 (2018).
- Y. guang Bi, Z. ting Lin, S. ting Deng, Fabrication and characterization of hydroxyapatite/sodium alginate/chitosan composite microspheres for drug delivery and bone tissue engineering, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C.*, 100, 576-583 (2019).
- D. Steinberg, M. Friedman, Sustained-release delivery of antimicrobial drugs for the treatment of periodontal diseases: Fantasy or already reality?, *Periodontol.*, 84, 176-187 (2020).
- I. Qayoom, R. Verma, P.A. Murugan, D.B. Raina, A.K. Teotia, S. Matheshwaran, N.N. Nair, M. Tägil, L. Lidgren, A. Kumar, A biphasic nanohydroxyapatite/calcium sulphate carrier containing Rifampicin and Isoniazid for local delivery gives sustained and effective antibiotic release and prevents biofilm formation, *Sci. Rep.*, 10, 14128 (2020).
- R.S. Byrne, P.B. Deasy, Use of commercial porous ceramic particles for sustained drug delivery, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 246, 61-73 (2002).
- A. Farzin, S.A. Etesami, A. Goodarzi, J. Ai, A facile way for development of three-dimensional localized drug delivery system for bone tissue engineering, *Mater. Sci. Eng. C.*, 105, 110032 (2019).
- A.P.S. Prasanna, G.D. Venkatasubbu, Sustained release of amoxicillin from hydroxyapatite nanocomposite for bone infections, *Prog. Biomater.*, 7, 289-296 (2018).
- Y. Zhu, K. Liu, J. Deng, J. Ye, F. Ai, H. Ouyang, T. Wu, J. Jia, X. Cheng, X. Wang, 3D printed zirconia ceramic hip joint with precise structure and broad-spectrum antibacterial properties, *Int. J. Nanomedicine.*, 14,

- 5977-5987 (2019).
33. R. Barkallah, R. Taktak, N. Guerhazi, K. Elleuch, J. bouaziz, Mechanical properties and wear behaviour of alumina/tricalcium phosphate/titania ceramics as coating for orthopedic implant, *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, 241, 107399 (2020).
 34. T. Kokubo, and H. Takadama, How useful is SBF in predicting in vivo bone bioactivity?, *Biomaterials*, 27, 2907-2915 (2006).
 35. S. Sasikumar, Effect of particle size of calcium phosphate based bioceramic drug delivery carrier on the release kinetics of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride: an in vitro study. *Front. Mater. Sci.*, 7, 261–268 (2013).
 36. S. Sasikumar and R. Vijayaraghavan, Synthesis and Characterization of Bioceramic Calcium Phosphates by Rapid Combustion Synthesis. *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.*, 26, 1114–1118 (2010).
 37. S. Sasikumar and R. Vijayaraghavan, Effect of metal-ion-to-fuel ratio on the phase formation of bioceramic phosphates synthesized by self-propagating combustion. *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.*, 9, 035003 (2008).
 38. C. F. Marques, A. C. Matos, I. A. C. Ribeiro, L. M. Goncalves, A. Bettencourt, J. M. F. Ferreira. Insights on the properties of levofloxacin-adsorbed Sr- and Mg- doped calcium phosphate powders. *J Mater Sci: Mater. Med.*, 27, 123 (2016).
 39. S. V. Blokhina, A. V. Sharapova, M. V. O'pkhovich, O. V. Volkova, G. L. Perlovich, Solubility, lipophilicity and membrane permeability of some fluoroquinolone antimicrobials. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 93, 29-37 (2016).
 40. V. S. Praptowidodo, Influence of swelling on water transport through PVA-based membrane. *J. Mol. Struct.*, 739, 1-3 (2015).
 41. U. Fumio, Y. Hiroshi, N. Kumiko, N. Sachihiko, S. Kenji, M. Yasunori, Swelling and mechanical properties of poly (vinyl alcohol) hydrogels. *Int. J. Pharm.*, 58, 135-142 (1990).
 42. S. Ghosh, R. S. K. Raju, N. Ghosh, K. Chaudhury, S. Ghosh, I. Banerjee, N. Pramanik, Development and physicochemical characterization of doxorubicin-encapsulated hydroxyapatite–polyvinyl alcohol nanocomposite for repair of osteosarcoma-affected bone tissues. *C. R. Chim.*, 22, 46-57 (2019).
 43. S. Zeng, S. Fu, G. Guo, H. Liang, Z. Qian, X. Tang, F. Luo, Preparation and characterization of nano-hydroxyapatite/poly(vinyl alcohol) composite membranes for guided bone regeneration. *J. Biomed. Nanotechnol.*, 7, 549-557 (2011).
 44. Y. Song, K. Lin, S. He, C. Wang, S. Zhang, D. Li, J. Wang, T. Cao, L. Bi, G. Pei, Nano-biphasic calcium phosphate/polyvinyl alcohol composites with enhanced bioactivity for bone repair via low-temperature three-dimensional printing and loading with platelet-rich fibrin. *Int. J. Nanomedicine.*, 13, 505-523 (2018).
 45. A. A. Ashraf, S. M. Zebarjad, M. J. Hadianfard, The cross-linked polyvinyl alcohol/hydroxyapatite nanocomposite foam. *J. Mater. Res. Technol.*, 8, 3149-3157 (2018).
 46. M. Catauro, F. Bollino, F. Papale, S. Pacifico, S. Galasso, C. Ferrara, P. Mustarelli. Synthesis of zirconia/polyethylene glycol hybrid materials by sol–gel processing and connections between structure and release kinetic of indomethacin. *Drug Delivery*, 21, 595-604 (2014).